

Quanti Farm

**ADVANCED DECISION
SUPPORT TOOL**

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FACTSHEET #7

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WHAT IS IT?

The **Advanced Decision Support Tool** is a structured decision-making component of the **Quanti Farm Toolkit** that supports the selection of the most appropriate **Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions (DATSs)** for a specific farm.

It applies a **multi-criteria assessment framework** that combines **Strategic Fit analysis, Quality Function Deployment (QFD), and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)** to evaluate DATSs against farm-specific goals, stakeholder needs, and contextual factors.

By systematically translating **qualitative preferences and strategic considerations** into **comparable decision scores**, the tool helps reduce uncertainty and supports **evidence-informed technology adoption decisions**.

WHO IS IT FOR?

The Advanced Decision Support Tool is designed for:

Farm Advisers and Consultants

supporting farmers in digitalisation decisions.

Farmers and Farm Managers

involved in structured technology selection processes.

Digital Innovation Hubs and Technology Facilitators

assisting farms in the adoption of DATSs.

Researchers and Innovation Stakeholders

analysing technology uptake drivers.

The tool is particularly suited to **advisor-led decision-making processes** that require a systematic and transparent evaluation approach.

KEY OBJECTIVES

To support the selection of DATSs that best fit farm-specific strategic goals and preferences

To **integrate farmers', customers', and partners' needs** into the decision-making process

To address uncertainty around the benefits, costs, and risks of digital technologies

To enable transparent and reproducible multi-criteria evaluation of DATSs

To reduce barriers to digital technology adoption through structured, evidence-based assessment

MAIN FEATURES

Multi-step decision framework

Guides users through a three-step process: **Strategic Fit filtering**, **QFD-based stakeholder needs assessment**, and **final ranking using AHP**.

Farm strategy alignment

Evaluates DATSs against predefined **farm strategic goals** (e.g., cost reduction, sustainability, risk reduction, innovation).

Stakeholder needs integration

Incorporates the needs of **customers and partners** (e.g., quality, traceability, consistency, sustainability) into the evaluation.

Multi-criteria evaluation and weighting

Applies structured weighting and pair-wise comparisons across **technological, organisational, environmental, benefit, and cost criteria**.

Transparent scoring and ranking of DATSs

Produces **comparable scores and rankings** that clearly indicate the most suitable DATS for a specific farm context.

Offline usability

Currently available as a **downloadable spreadsheet-based tool**, enabling offline

Together, these features support **robust, transparent, and farm-centred decision making** for digital technology adoption.

Learn
More

quantifarm.eu
info@quantifarm.eu

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